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CDKN activation is a defining feature of cellular senescence.

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Transcriptional activation of genes encoding the cyclin dependent kinase inhibitors (*CDKN*) was a defining feature of cellular senescence.

Results

We measured total transcription in young and senescent human umbilical vein endothelial (HUVEC) cells to understand, study and comprehensively define the senescence program in *Homo sapiens*. We discovered activation of the *CDKN* gene family as an essential component of senescence in human cells (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Activation of *CDKN* genes is an essential component of the senescence program.

GSE155680

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1029	8.13E-177	0.0916	-28.351005	-2.597939	606.28	CDKN2A	94/15580	99.4
1026	5.60E-58	0.0541	-16.051284	-0.868774	10072.35	CDKN1A	646/15580	95.9
1033	2.80E-56	0.1255	15.806546	1.983961	256.9	CDKN3	676/15580	95.7
1030	1.72E-48	0.1068	-14.633448	-1.562674	376.78	CDKN2B	798/15580	94.9
1028	1.53E-06	0.3141	-4.80787	-1.510151	34.44	CDKN1C	5103/15580	67.2

Activation of genes encoding the cyclin dependent kinase (CDK) inhibitor (CDKN) family was a transcriptional feature of senescence in human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) (Figure 1). This included CDKN2A, CDKN1A, CDKN2B, and CDKN1C.

We studied a second cellular model of senescence wherein we measured total transcription in fibroblasts isolated from children and elderly humans to define the human senescence program in an unbiased fashion (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Activation of *CDKN* genes is an essential component of the senescence program.

GSE262932

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1030	1.41E-23	0.282	-10.007655	-2.8231883	237.86	CDKN2B	427/17001	97.5
1031	3.72E-10	0.224	-6.265398	-1.403854	385.2	CDKN2C	1312/17001	92.3
1029	4.07E-09	0.635	-5.8811292	-3.7367996	51.72	CDKN2A	1517/17001	91.1
1028	1.03E-04	0.503	-3.8834926	-1.9531892	60.66	CDKN1C	3371/17001	80.2
1033	2.84E-01	0.266	1.0718418	0.2846982	150.97	CDKN3	11524/17001	32.2

In this second model, activation of *CDKN* genes was again a defining element of the senescence gene signature.

Discussion

We described here the discovery of activation of the cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor (*CDKN*) gene family as an essential component of the senescence program in humans.